

Settings for namelist.input of configuration of run 1

&time_control	
run_days	0
run_hours	0
run_minutes	0
run_seconds	0
start_year	2020, 2020, 2020
start_month	03, 03, 03
start_day	18, 18, 18
start_hour	12, 12, 12
end_year	2020, 2020, 2020
end_month	03, 03, 03
end_day	21, 21, 21
end_hour	06, 06, 06
interval_seconds	21600
input_from_file	.true., .true., .true.
history_interval	60, 60, 60
frames_per_outfile	1000, 1000, 1000
restart	.false.
restart_interval	7200
io_form_history	2
io_form_restart	2
io_form_input	2
io_form_boundary	2
debug_level	0
history_outname	/lustre/nobackup/WUR/ESG/welli009/run1/wrfout_d<domain>.<date>
&domains	
time_step	60
time_step_fract_num	0
time_step_fract_den	1
max_dom	3
e_we	300, 996, 551
e_sn	226, 246, 246
e_vert	61, 61, 61
eta_levels	1.0000, 0.9968, 0.9919, ..., 0.00000
p_top_requested	1000
num_metgrid_levels	38
num_metgrid_soil_levels	4
dx	10000, 2000, 2000
dy	10000, 2000, 2000
grid_id	1, 2, 3
parent_id	1, 1, 1
i_parent_start	1, 50, 90
j_parent_start	1, 15, 80
parent_grid_ratio	1, 5, 5
parent_time_step_ratio	1, 3, 3
feedback	1
smooth_option	0
use_adaptive_time_step	.true.
max_ts_locs	20

&physics	
mp_physics	4, 4, 4
cu_physics	1, 0, 0
ra_lw_physics	4, 4, 4
ra_sw_physics	2, 2, 2
bl_pbl_physics	2, 2, 2
sf_sfclay_physics	2, 2, 2
sf_surface_physics	2, 2, 2
radt	15, 15, 15
bldt	0, 0, 0
cutd	0, 0, 0
isfflx	1
icloud	1
ifsnow	1
surface_input_source	1
num_soil_layers	4
num_land_cat	21
maxiens	1
maxens	3
maxens2	3
maxens3	16
ensdim	144
sf_urban_physics	0, 0, 0
topo_wind	0
&fdda	
&dynamics	
hybrid_opt	2
w_damping	1
diff_opt	1, 1, 1
km_opt	4, 4, 4
diff_6th_opt	0, 0, 0
diff_6th_factor	0.12, 0.12, 0.12
base_temp	290.
damp_opt	0
zdamp	7500., 7500., 7500.
dampcoef	0.2, 0.2, 0.2
khdif	0, 0, 0
kvdif	0, 0, 0
non_hydrostatic	.true., .true., .true.
moist_adv_opt	1, 1, 1
scalar_adv_opt	1, 1, 1
gwd_opt	1
chem_adv_opt	2, 2, 2
&bdy_control	
spec_bdy_width	5
spec_zone	1
relax_zone	4
specified	.true., .false., .false.

nested	.false., .true., .true., .true.
&grib2	
(none)	
&chem	
chem_opt	0, 0, 0
emiss_opt	0, 0, 0
chem_in_opt	0, 0, 0
io_style_emissions	2
kemit	15
have_bcs_chem	.true., .true., .true.
gas_drydep_opt	0, 0, 0
aer_drydep_opt	1, 1, 1
bio_emiss_opt	0, 0, 0
emiss_inpt_opt	16, 16, 16
biomass_burn_opt	0, 0, 0
dust_opt	0
seas_opt	0
dmsemis_opt	0
gaschem_onoff	0, 0, 0
aerchem_onoff	0, 0, 0
wetscav_onoff	0, 0, 0
cldchem_onoff	0, 0, 0
vertmix_onoff	1, 1, 1
chem_conv_tr	0, 0, 0
aer_ra_feedback	0, 0, 0
&namelist_quilt	
nio_tasks_per_group	0
nio_groups	1